

Dielectric Strength Testing of 3D Printed Plastics and Application to a High Voltage Transformer Pulser*

D. M. French, J. P. O'Loughlin, B. W. Hoff[‡], S. Maestas, D. Lepell⁺, T. Montoya⁺⁺

*Air Force Research Laboratory, Directed Energy Directorate
Kirtland AFB, New Mexico, USA*

Abstract

The use of additive manufacturing techniques offers the potential to rapidly fabricate complex insulator designs; however, the lack of dielectric strength data for many of the currently available printable plastics limits the usefulness of these materials in high electric field environments. The authors begin to address this issue by providing data from dielectric strength testing of selected plastic samples fabricated using the stereolithography (SLA), fused deposition modeling (FDM), and selective laser sintering (SLS) additive manufacturing techniques. Results of a high voltage transformer experiment using an SLA printed winding form will be presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

A high voltage pulsed power supply capable of generating 180 kV into a 1000 Ω load was needed for testing of electron beam driven microwave tubes. The requirements for the electron beam are a relatively flat voltage pulse and the ability to adjust the output voltage. For these reasons, a transformer based system was chosen which will allow the charge voltage and pulse shape on a pulse forming network (PFN) to be adjusted.

As with many engineering projects, with high voltage insulation the part that is built is sometimes different from that which is considered ideal due to manufacturing constraints. One of these cases is in the transformer windings. While one can design an ideal winding shape, this can be costly or difficult to manufacture. With the increasing adoption of additive manufacturing (AM) or 3D printing many designs which were previously unrealizable or required multiple manufacturing steps can now be quickly and economically produced.

As both a proof of concept, and to simplify the construction of the transformer, stereolithography (SLA) was used to manufacture the winding form for the transformer. The SLA approach allows the designer to easily include arbitrary tapers, voids, and other geometric features which can be difficult or impossible to machine.

In this case, a groove in which the secondary winding sits is directly printed on the part simplifying the assembly of the transformer. In addition to the secondary winding, voids, or passthroughs can be printed in insulating parts allowing for convenient routing of high voltage conductors providing more ideal connection locations.

II. PULSER DESIGN

The energy requirement for a 180kV, 1 μ s pulse in a 1k Ω load, is 32.4 Joules. The approach that is used is a PFN and a step-up transformer. The capacitors for the PFN are rated at 2.1nF and 50kV, giving 2.625 Joules per capacitor. For a $\sim$ 70% efficiency this design will therefore require 18 capacitors. The nine section type-E PFN uses two capacitors, 4.2 nF, per section. The design is intended for single pulse operation, with an inter pulse time of at least one minute. Given the pulse and core characteristics, the primary is determined as 9 turns and the secondary as 70 turns. The winding configuration is a double basket as shown in Figure 1. An existing transformer core was reused for this pulser. The core has a 5.08 cm x 5.08 cm cross section, the window is 25.4 cm x 8.89 cm, and the outside core dimensions of 35.56 cm x 19.05 cm. The B-H curve was measured at 60 Hz, Figure 2, and the core has a B_{sat} of approximately 1 T, which is consistent with nanocrystalline core material.

Figure 1. Double basket configuration for the secondary windings.

* Work supported by the Air Force Research Laboratory

[‡] email: afrl.deh.workflow@us.af.mil

⁺ Leidos, Albuquerque, NM

⁺⁺ Voss Scientific, Albuquerque, NM

Figure 2. B-H measurement at 60 Hz.

Figure 3. Transformer core with winding forms.

The transformer winding form was printed using the stereolithography (SLA) technique with Somos WaterShed XC 11122 resin. The manufacturer data indicates a dielectric constant of 3.5 per ASTM D150 and a dielectric strength approximately equal to 15.5 kV/mm per ASTM D149. The winding forms are in two pieces, a center form on which the primary tape is wound and an outer form on which the secondary coils are wound. The primary winding form contains a pass-through for one of the primary leads to pass which is visible in Figure 3. This configuration allows for both positive and negative primary connections to be made on the same side of the transformer. The parallel primary windings consist of 9 turns of 15.24 cm wide, 0.0508 mm thick copper, insulated with 2 layers of 2-mil Mylar. The secondary winding forms slide over the completed primary forms and contain provisions for corona rings in the center and lugs for making the ground connections on the ends. Grooves to guide the 20 gauge magnet wire for the four parallel secondary coils were printed directly into the part. This greatly simplified the winding of the transformer and the built in lugs provided a robust means of terminating the secondary windings. The assembled transformer is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Fully assembled transformer with ground connected to printed lugs and the corona rings installed into printed channel.

The transformer coupling, $k = (1 - L_{ps}/L_p)^{1/2}$, where L_p is the primary inductance with the secondary open and L_{ps} is the primary inductance when the secondary shorted, was measured with an LCR meter. The same measurement was made on the secondary with the primary both open and shorted. The resulting low frequency coupling coefficients of ~99.25% are displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Transformer coupling measured on both the primary and secondary.

The pulse transformer is driven by a 9 section type-E PFN. The PFN design is derived from an ideal type-E network with N_s sections, pulse duration τ , and characteristic impedance Z , where $C = \tau/2ZN_s$ and $L =$

Z^2C . The inductors for the type-E network are wound on a common solenoid and the capacitors are tapped off at the appropriate locations. The inductance of a single layer solenoid of radius a meters and length b meters with N turns is

$$L(a, b, N) = 39.37 \left(\frac{a^2 N^2}{9a + 10b} \right) \mu H. \quad (1)$$

The coupling coefficient is related by considering two adjacent sections of the PFN. The sections have equal inductance, radii, lengths, and turns given by L_2 . The total inductance of these two equal inductors in series is

$$L(a, 2b, 2N) = 2L_2(1 + k). \quad (2)$$

Using the above and defining the ratio $b/a = \alpha$, the coupling coefficient $k(\alpha)$ can be solved for with

$$k(\alpha) = \frac{1}{1 + 2.22\alpha}. \quad (3)$$

For an ideal type-E PFN, $k = 0.15$, therefore, $\alpha = 2.6 = b/a$. For the present design $\tau = 1 \mu s$, $N_s = 9$, $C = 4.2 \text{ nF}$, and $Z = 14 \Omega$. This gives $L = 858 \text{ nH}$ and with the known b/a of 2.6 for $N = 8$ turns $a = 1.15 \text{ cm}$ and $b = 3 \text{ cm}$.

III. PULSER ASSEMBLY AND TESTING

The fully assembled laboratory “breadboard” pulser is shown in Figure 6 with the PFN and spark gap switch visible at the right. The pulser is housed in a tank which is filled with Diala transformer oil after pulling a rough vacuum on the tank. Once filled with oil, the tank is roughed to a pressure of a few 100s mTorr and left for several hours to remove all air from the transformer, the tank is then vented to atmosphere and the process is repeated several times until no significant numbers of bubbles are seen.

The transformer was tested into a load resistance of $\sim 1700 \Omega$. Starting from a PFN charge voltage of 10 kV, the voltage was increased in 5 kV increments to a maximum of 50 kV. No breakdown was observed during this process and the pulser operated very reliably for these initial shots. Figure 7 shows an overlay of 10 shots at full PFN charge voltage of 50kV resulting in an output of $>200 \text{ kV}$ into 1700Ω . The overshoot and droop can likely be corrected by adjusting the PFN, however, this will be performed when the electron beam gun is installed to account for the diode capacitance.

Figure 6. Assembled pulser system with PFN and the transformer installed.

Figure 7. Overlay of 10 shots at 50 kV PFN charge.

IV. MATERIAL SELECTION

Dielectric strength data for resins associated with three different printing methods, stereolithography (SLA), fused deposition modeling (FDM), and selective laser sintering (SLS), were evaluated as part of the selection process for the transformer winding form. Detailed descriptions of these processes are available in the published literature [1-3] as well as various vendor websites. The dielectric strength information was sourced from ASTM D149 [4] standard testing data provided by the manufacturers. Because build volumes and layer resolution for state of the art SLA, FDM, and SLS printing systems are roughly equivalent (layer resolutions of ~0.15 mm and build volumes ~1 m), the primary selection criteria used were dielectric strength, availability, and transparency. Transparency was chosen to be a criterion due to the fact that should breakdown occur, it could be more easily diagnosed.

Manufacturer ASTM D149 data for selected FDM printed plastics [5-14] are displayed in Figure 8. As indicated by the data, there was a large disparity (in some cases, greater than a factor of 3) in measured dielectric strength of the printed FDM test pieces depending on the print direction use for the test piece. Dielectric strength data for selected SLS thermoplastics [15-19] and SLA photopolymers [20-34] are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10, respectively.

Figure 8. Dielectric strength data for FDM resins printed in the XZ and ZX directions.

Figure 9. Dielectric strength data for printed SLS resins.

Figure 10. Dielectric strength data for printed SLA resins.

The FDM-printed dielectrics were considered to be the least desirable for fabrication of the transformer winding form due to the sizeable disparity in dielectric strength for the different printing orientations. Additionally, even the highest performing FDM plastics in the most favorable orientations tended to have lower dielectric strengths than the majority of SLA or SLS plastics. The majority of SLS and SLA plastics, for which data were available, had dielectric strengths between 15 and 18.5 kV/mm (per ASTM D149).

Since all of the SLS materials evaluated were opaque when printed, the highest performing transparent resin immediately available to the authors was the SLA WaterShed XC 11122 resin (~15.5 kV/mm). It is important to note that published ASTM D149 data for common conventionally fabricated plastics like polypropylene (~24 kV/mm), low density polyethylene (~22 kV/mm), and Teflon (20 kV/mm) [35] exceed even the best performing printed plastics evaluated in the present study.

V. CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated that the use of 3D printing provides an economically and technically viable means for the construction of high voltage pulse transformers. This example also obviously carries over to high voltage transformers in general. Printed insulators tend to have lower dielectric strengths than those made using conventionally fabricated plastics; however, in cases

where expected electric field stresses are adequately addressed by the dielectric strength of printed materials, they are a potentially superior choice to conventional plastics.

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